

THE PROBLEM OF ISOMORPHISM OF LABELED SIMPLE GRAPHS OF ORDER n , FOR $n < 6$

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Abstract. Let V be a finite set and E a subset of its 2-element subsets. Then the pair $Y = (V, E)$ is called a simple graph with vertex set V and edge set E . Vertices u and v in graph $Y = (V, E)$ are called adjacent if Y contains a $a(u, v) := \{u, v\}$ edge. And in this case, the vertices u and v are said to be incident to this edge. Graphs $Y_1 = (V_1, E_1)$ and $Y_2 = (V_2, E_2)$ are isomorphic if there exists a one-to-one correspondence between their vertex sets such that two vertices are connected by an edge in one graph if and only if their corresponding vertices are connected by an edge in the other graph. This paper presents a detailed solution to the problem of isomorphism of labeled simple graphs of small orders using methods of invariant theory.

Keywords: simple graph, group, invariant.

Introduction. The results of this study were announced in [1]. The problem of graph isomorphism and related algorithmic issues are studied in detail in [2]. The monograph [3] discusses applications of invariant theory to problems in the differential geometry of classical groups.

Let G be a finite group and X an n -dimensional vector space. Assume $|G| = n$. The action of the group G on X is defined as a homomorphism $\alpha: G \rightarrow S(X)$, where $S(X)$ is the group of all invertible linear transformations of X into itself. The action of the group G on X is denoted by $\alpha(g) = g \circ x$ (or gx). Homomorphism for α means $(g_1 g_2) \circ x = (g_1 (g_2 x))$, where $g_1, g_2 \in G, x \in X$. The set $G(x) = \{gx \mid g \in G\}$ is called the *orbit* of the point $x \in X$. Clearly, $|G(x)| \leq n$. A numerical function $f: X \rightarrow k$ is called *invariant* under the action of G on X if for all $g \in G$ and $x \in X$, we have $f(gx) = f(x)$, where k is the field of real or complex numbers.

Points $x, y \in X$ are called equivalent if there exists $g \in G$ such that $gx = y$, i.e. $G(x) = G(y)$.

Theorem 1.1. For elements $x, y \in X$, the equality $G(x) = G(y)$ holds if and only if every invariant polynomial f takes the same values on orbits of points x and y .

Proof. If $G(x) = G(y)$, then clearly every invariant polynomial takes the same value on $G(x)$ and $G(y)$.

Conversely, suppose every invariant polynomial takes the same values on $G(x)$ and $G(y)$. Then we will prove that $G(x) = G(y)$. Assume the contrary, that $G(x) \neq G(y)$. Let $G(x) = \{x_1, \dots, x_k\}$ and $G(y) = \{y_1, \dots, y_m\}$, where $k \leq n$ and $m \leq n$. Then, by Lagrange interpolation, there exists a polynomial P (not necessarily invariant) such that takes 0 on $G(x)$ and 1 on $G(y)$. Then the polynomial

$$\tilde{P}(z) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{g \in G} P(gz)$$

is invariant and takes values 0 and 1 on $G(x)$ and $G(y)$, respectively, which contradicts the assumption. \diamond

Consider a labeled graph Y of order n , i.e., Y is a graph whose vertices are assigned natural numbers from 1 to n . Let us now consider the set X consisting of functions x_{ij} , where i and j independently range from 1 to n , defined as follows:

$$x_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if vertices } i \text{ and } j \text{ are connected by an edge,} \\ 0, & \text{if vertices } i \text{ and } j \text{ are not connected by an edge.} \end{cases}$$

As the group G , we take the group of all permutations of the set $N_n = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$, i.e., $G = S_n$, the symmetric group of order n .

The action of the group S_n on X defined as follows: for each $g \in S_n$, $(gx_{ij}) = x_{g(i)g(j)}$, where $i, j \in N_n$.

Consider a polynomial $f(x_{11}, x_{12}, \dots, x_{nn})$ where i and j independently range from 1 to n . $f(x_{11}, x_{12}, \dots, x_{nn})$ is called S_n -invariant if for any $g \in S_n$, the following equality holds:

$$f(x_{11}, x_{12}, \dots, x_{nn}) = f(x_{g(1)g(1)}, x_{g(1)g(2)}, \dots, x_{g(n)g(n)}).$$

Obviously, the sum and product of S_n -invariant polynomials are S_n -invariant polynomials. Thus, the set of all S_n -invariant polynomials forms an algebra, which we denote by $Z[x_{11}, x_{12}, \dots, x_{nn}]^{S_n}$.

Consider all S_n -invariant polynomials without constant terms. They form a subalgebra in the algebra $Z[x_{11}, x_{12}, \dots, x_{nn}]^{S_n}$, which we denote by $I[n]$.

The set of S_n -invariant polynomials such that any S_n -invariant polynomial can be represented as a polynomial in the elements of this set is called an integral rational basis in $I[n]$. An integral rational basis is minimal if it contains the minimum number of elements from the possible number of elements in this set.

From the definition of an integral rational basis and Theorem 1.1, we obtain the following theorem.

Theorem 1.2. For any $x, y \in X$, the equality $S_n(x) = S_n(y)$ holds if and only if the elements of some integral rational basis take the same values on $S_n(x)$ and $S_n(y)$.

From this, it follows that the problem of isomorphism of labeled simple graphs reduces to finding an integral rational basis in the algebra $I[n]$.

For the cases $n = 3, n = 4$, and $n = 5$, we will indicate the minimal integral rational bases of the algebra $I[n]$ (the integral rational basis for the cases $n = 3, n = 4$, and $n = 5$ consists of three, ten, and thirty-three, and the minimal basis consists of one, three, and four S_n -invariant polynomials, respectively) and, using Theorem 1.2, we will solve the problem of isomorphism of labeled simple graphs with three, four, and five vertices.

Isomorphism of Labeled Simple Graphs with Three and Four Vertices. Let Y be a graph with three vertices. We define an integral rational basis in the algebra $I[3]$. Consider the following S_3 -invariant polynomials on the graph Y :

$$I_1(Y) = \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq 3} x_{ij};$$

$$I_2(Y) = \sum x_{12} x_{13},$$

where Σ is the symmetrization over all indices 1, 2, and 3;

$$I_3(Y) = x_{12} x_{13} x_{23}.$$

These polynomials correspond to the following graphs:

Since simple graphs on three vertices are exhausted by the ones shown above, any S_3 -invariant polynomial is a sum and product of the invariants I_1, I_2, I_3 .

Note that the value of $I_1(Y)$ determines the number of edges in the graph Y .

Elementary calculations show that the following relations hold between these invariants, for example:

$$I_2 = \frac{1}{2}(I_1^2 - I_1); \quad I_3 = \frac{1}{6}(I_1^3 - 3I_1^2 + 2I_1).$$

Therefore, the polynomial I_1 forms a minimal integral rational basis in the algebra $I[3]$.

Theorem 2. 1. Graphs Y_1 and Y_2 with three vertices are isomorphic if and only if the invariant I_1 takes the same value on them, i.e., $I_1(Y_1) = I_1(Y_2)$.

The proof follows directly from Theorem 1.1.

Next, let Y be a graph with four vertices. We define a full rational basis in the algebra $I[4]$. Let us consider the following S_4 -invariant polynomials on the graph Y :

$$\begin{aligned} I_1(Y) &= \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq 4} x_{ij}, \\ I_2(Y) &= \sum x_{12} x_{13}, \\ I_3(Y) &= \sum x_{12} x_{34}, \\ I_4(Y) &= \sum x_{12} x_{13} x_{14}, \\ I_5(Y) &= \sum x_{12} x_{13} x_{23}, \\ I_6(Y) &= \sum x_{12} x_{13} x_{24}, \\ I_7(Y) &= \sum x_{12} x_{13} x_{14} x_{23}, \\ I_8(Y) &= \sum x_{12} x_{13} x_{24} x_{34}, \\ I_9(Y) &= \sum x_{12} x_{13} x_{14} x_{23} x_{24}, \\ I_{10}(Y) &= x_{12} x_{13} x_{24} x_{34}, \end{aligned}$$

where the symbol \sum denotes symmetrization over all indices 1, 2, 3, and 4. The following graphs correspond to these polynomials:

Since all simple graphs with four vertices are exhausted by the ones listed above, any invariant polynomial is a sum and product of the invariants I_1 through I_{10} .

Elementary computations show that there are, for example, the following relationships among these invariant polynomials:

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_3 &= \frac{1}{2}(I_1^2 - I_1 - 2I_2), & I_5 &= \frac{1}{3}(3I_1I_2 + 3I_1^2 - I_1^3 - 6I_2 - 2I_1 - 3I_4), \\
 I_6 &= \frac{1}{2}(I_1^3 - 3I_1^2) - I_1I_2 + I_1 + 2I_2, & I_7 &= I_1I_4 - 3I_4, \\
 I_8 &= \frac{1}{8}(I_1^4 - 6I_1^3 - 2I_1^2I_2 + 11I_1^2 + 10I_1I_2 - 6I_1 - 12I_2 - 4I_1I_4 + 12I_4), \\
 I_9 &= \frac{1}{2}(I_2I_4 - 2I_1I_4 + 3I_4), & I_{10} &= \frac{1}{12}(I_1I_2I_4 - 2I_1^2I_4 + 13I_1I_4 - 5I_2I_4 - 15I_4).
 \end{aligned}$$

To prove the independence of the invariant polynomials I_1, I_2, I_4 , we construct a table of their values.

Number of edges Invariant polynomial	1	2	2	3	3	3	4	4	5	6
I_1	1	2	2	3	3	3	4	4	5	6
I_2	0	1	0	3	3	2	5	4	8	12
I_4	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	2	4

From this table, it is evident that the S_4 -invariant polynomials I_1, I_2 , and I_4 are linearly independent.

Therefore, the polynomials I_1, I_2 , and I_4 form a minimal integral rational basis in the algebra $I[4]$.

Theorem 2. 2. Graphs Y_1 and Y_2 with four vertices are isomorphic if and only if the S_4 -invariant polynomials I_1, I_2 , and I_4 take the same values, i.e., $I_1(Y_1) = I_1(Y_2)$, $I_2(Y_1) = I_2(Y_2)$, and $I_4(Y_1) = I_4(Y_2)$.

The proof directly follows from Theorem 1.1.

Isomorphism of labeled simple graphs with five vertices. Let Y be a graph with five vertices. We define an integral rational basis in the algebra $I[5]$. Consider the following S_5 -invariant polynomials on the graph Y :

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_1(Y) &= \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq 5} x_{ij}; & I_2(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}, & I_3(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{34}; \\
 I_4(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}x_{i4}, & I_5(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}x_{24}, & I_6(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}x_{23}, \\
 I_7(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}x_{45}; & I_8(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}x_{14}x_{15}, & I_9(Y) &= x_{12}x_{13}x_{14}x_{23}, \\
 I_{10}(Y) &= x_{12}x_{13}x_{24}x_{34}, & I_{11}(Y) &= x_{12}x_{23}x_{34}x_{45}, \\
 I_{12}(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}x_{23}x_{45}, & I_{13}(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}x_{14}x_{25}; \\
 I_{14}(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}x_{14}x_{23}x_{34}, & I_{15}(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}x_{14}x_{34}x_{45}, \\
 I_{16}(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}x_{24}x_{34}x_{45}, & I_{17}(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}x_{14}x_{23}x_{45}, \\
 I_{18}(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}x_{14}x_{15}x_{45}, & I_{19}(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}x_{24}x_{35}x_{45}; \\
 I_{20}(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}x_{14}x_{15}x_{23}x_{45}, & I_{21}(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}x_{14}x_{15}x_{23}x_{24}, \\
 I_{22}(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}x_{14}x_{23}x_{24}x_{34}, & I_{23}(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}x_{14}x_{23}x_{25}x_{45}, \\
 I_{24}(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}x_{14}x_{25}x_{35}x_{45}, & I_{25}(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}x_{14}x_{23}x_{24}x_{35}; \\
 I_{26}(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}x_{14}x_{15}x_{23}x_{34}x_{45}, & I_{27}(Y) &= \sum_{12} x_{13}x_{14}x_{15}x_{23}x_{24}x_{25}, \\
 I_{28}(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}x_{14}x_{15}x_{23}x_{24}x_{34}, & I_{29}(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}x_{14}x_{23}x_{25}x_{34}x_{45}; \\
 I_{30}(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}x_{14}x_{15}x_{23}x_{34}x_{35}x_{45}, & I_{31}(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}x_{14}x_{15}x_{23}x_{25}x_{34}x_{45}; \\
 I_{32}(Y) &= \sum x_{12}x_{13}x_{14}x_{15}x_{23}x_{24}x_{25}x_{34}x_{35};
 \end{aligned}$$

$$I_{33}(Y) = \sum x_{12} x_{13} x_{14} x_{15} x_{23} x_{24} x_{25} x_{34} x_{35} x_{45},$$

where Σ is the symmetrization over all indices 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5. The corresponding graphs for these polynomials are easy to visualize. Since simple graphs with five vertices are exhausted by these graphs, any S_5 -invariant polynomial is a sum and product of the invariants I_1 through I_{33} .

To identify a minimal integral rational basis, it is easy to construct a table of values of the polynomials I_1 through I_{33} on $I[5]$, and by studying it, one can be convinced that the invariant polynomials $I_1, I_2, I_4,$ and I_5 form a minimal integral rational basis in the algebra $I[5]$.

Theorem 3.1. Graphs Y_1 and Y_2 with five vertices are isomorphic if and only if the S_5 -invariant polynomials $I_1, I_2, I_4,$ and I_5 take the same values on them, i.e., $I_1(Y_1) = I_1(Y_2), I_2(Y_1) = I_2(Y_2), I_4(Y_1) = I_4(Y_2),$ and $I_5(Y_1) = I_5(Y_2)$.

The proof directly follows from Theorem 1.2.

Conclusion: The results and methods of this article can be used in solving problems in graph theory and pattern recognition theory.

References

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